

Towards a Green Economy: Multisectoral Assessment of Renewable Energy Expansion and Input-Output Analysis of the Dominican Energy Matrix

Green Economy and Energy Shift in the Dominican Republic

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Executive Summary

This study critically examines the dynamics of energy demand and its environmental implications within the Dominican Republic's energy sector, using the MARIO model for a comprehensive multisectoral analysis. Key findings indicate that despite the integration of renewable energy sources, the surge in energy demand under the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario leads to a significant increase in greenhouse gas emissions. This underscores the urgent need for enhanced energy efficiency and the implementation of robust decarbonization strategies across all sectors to mitigate the adverse effects of rising demand.

Recommendations for actionable steps include:

Prioritizing investments in energy efficiency technologies and initiatives across various sectors to reduce overall energy consumption without hindering economic growth.

Expanding the use of multisectoral analytical models like MARIO to thoroughly assess and account for collateral emissions in sectoral expansion plans, ensuring a holistic approach to environmental impact assessment.

Strengthening policy frameworks to support the adoption of renewable energy sources and to incentivize the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, thereby aligning national energy practices with global decarbonization goals.

1. Introduction

In today's world, where changing the way we use energy is more important than ever, this report takes a close look at how energy is shared and used in different industries, with a special focus on the Dominican Republic. We used detailed information from well-known sources like the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), the Dominican Coordinating Body (OC), EORA, and Our World in Data to understand the energy sector's current situation and its impact on the environment.

The main idea of this study is to not worry about the costs of changing the energy system. Instead, we concentrate on how energy moves around and what it means for the environment. This way of looking at things helps us see how different parts of the economy work together to make energy use better and more sustainable, without getting stuck on how much it might cost to change things.

This report aims to show the patterns of how energy is used and made in the Dominican Republic and to look at how renewable energy could help us face worldwide environmental challenges. By covering everything from how energy is produced to its effect on climate change, this document wants to be a useful tool for people making policies, researchers, and anyone interested in moving towards a future where we use energy in a smarter, more sustainable way.

2. Methodology

DATABASES

OC - Coordinating Body

The Coordinating Body (OC) plays a crucial role as the operator of the electricity market and is responsible for the planning of operations in the Dominican Republic. This entity ensures efficient, safe, and equitable management of the National Electric System, coordinating the generation, transmission, and distribution of electrical energy. Through its platform, the OC provides valuable information about the operations of the electricity market, including data on energy generation from both renewable sources and fossil fuels, and other aspects relevant to the analysis of the electricity sector.

CEPALSTAT

The Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) is a United Nations entity focused on promoting economic and social development in the region. Its database, CEPALSTAT, collects varied information on economics, demography, environment, and more, serving as a reliable source for analyzing regional trends and challenges. Its broad thematic scope and accessibility make CEPALSTAT an invaluable

tool for researchers, policymakers, and the public interested in Latin American and Caribbean progress.

EORA

Eora is a global database that presents a multi-regional input-output (MRIO) table model, covering 190 countries and 15,909 sectors. It offers a time series from 1990 to 2022 and contains over 2700 environmental indicators, enabling complex analyses of global economic interactions and their environmental impact. Eora is essential for studying globalization, economic interdependencies, trade flows, as well as for tracking CO2 emissions and planning sustainable policies.

Our World in Data

Founded in 2013 by Max Roser, it is a research project dedicated to presenting empirical data and analyses on global development through accessible visualizations. This project covers a wide range of critical topics such as global health, economic development, education, environment, technology, innovation, and demography, noted for its focus on accessibility and information transparency. By collaborating with experts and academics to ensure data reliability and constant updates, Our World in Data becomes an essential platform for researchers, policymakers, and the general public, facilitating the understanding of complex global dynamics and promoting an informed dialogue on humanity's challenges and progress.

Methodology step by step

To incorporate the assumption that the installation cost of the energy matrix change is not considered in your methodology, and to evaluate the sectorial flow exchange of energy production, the methodology can be modified as follows:

In this study's methodology, the 2016 ECLAC database was used as the primary source for the detailed analysis of sectoral exchange, represented in standardized tables. This initial step allowed for the construction of the MARIO matrices, which were later adapted in Excel to formulate the System of Use and Supply (SUT) matrices, including the Intersectoral Transaction Flow Matrix (Z), the Final Demand Matrix (Y), the Production Factor Transaction Flow Matrix (V), and the Satellite Transaction Flow Matrix (E).

To complement this analysis and provide a more holistic view of the country's energy matrix, relevant information about the energy generated in the base year 2016, obtained from the Coordinating Body (OC), was integrated. This dataset included specific details about energy generation, broken down by renewable sources and fossil fuels, which was crucial for assessing the environmental and energy impact of different sectoral activities.

A key assumption of this study is that the installation cost of changing the energy matrix is not considered when evaluating the sectorial flow exchange of energy production. This methodological decision is based on focusing exclusively on analyzing energy flows and associated environmental impacts, without delving into the financial aspects of changing energy infrastructure.

The lack of tracking equivalent greenhouse gas emissions in CO₂ in the ECLAC database led to the integration of additional data from the EORA database into the E Matrix. To validate the accuracy of these emissions, a comparison of the GDP reported in the ECLAC database with figures from Our World in Data was conducted, followed by a comparative analysis of emissions with EORA data.

This triangulation process between the ECLAC, EORA databases, and the information from the Coordinating Body ensured consistency in considering comparable variables in the studied activities and commodities. It was noted that the ECLAC database contained a wider range of activities compared to EORA, leading to a meticulous mapping and categorization process of these activities based on their production factors, assuming a direct relationship between these factors and the resulting emissions from activities.

In conclusion, the E environmental extension matrix was developed, incorporating the activities identified in the ECLAC database along with emissions from the EORA database, and enriched with specific data on energy generation from the base year 2016 provided by the Coordinating Body. This approach allowed for a comprehensive assessment of emissions associated with each sector, providing an integral perspective on the energy and environmental dynamics involved, without considering the installation costs associated with changing the energy matrix.

Scenarios

The scenarios considered for the study project different growth trajectories and changes in the composition of electricity generation in the Dominican Republic towards 2035, starting from the supply demand in 2016, where electricity generated from non-fossil sources represented 11.63% and that from fossil sources 88.37%, totaling 15.79 TWh with GHG emissions of 8.18 MtCO₂.

Table 1. Scenarios

SCENARIO	NON-FOSSIL GENERATION (GWH AND %)	FOSSIL GENERATION (GWH AND %)	CO2 EMISSIONS (MTCO2)	SCENARIO PARTICULARS
Baseline 2016	1,836.60 GWh (11.63%)	13,956.10 GWh (88.37%)	8.18	Reference data for comparison with future scenarios.
BAU 2035	3,673.45 GWh (11.63%)	27,914.13 GWh (88.37%)	330.14	Scenario with no significant changes in the energy matrix, maintaining the proportion of non-fossil and fossil sources. Increase in demand and emissions due to economic and demographic growth.
Scenario 1A - Trend increase	6,016.54 GWh (19.00%)	25,649.46 GWh (81.00%)	303.88	Increase in the participation of non-fossil sources. Emphasizes the stability of marginal costs post-2025 and lower risk of deficit thanks to new installations. Limited participation of renewable energies, not exceeding 5000 GWh/year.
Scenario 1B - Alternative increase	6,304.20 GWh (19.00%)	26,875.80 GWh (81.00%)	332.93	Higher demand growth. Higher marginal costs and greater risk of shortage. Importance of oil derivatives in the energy matrix, with an increase in their participation up to 12% by 2035.
Scenario 2A - Trend increase	15,134.35 GWh (55.00%)	12,382.65 GWh (45.00%)	101.53	Strong focus on non-fossil sources, achieving a 55% participation. Minimal risk of shortage and marginal costs below 50 US\$/MWh during the day. Compliance with energy policies with 25% supply by NCRE in 2025 and 30% in 2030.
Scenario 2B - Alternative increase	17,378.68 GWh (44.00%)	22,118.32 GWh (56.00%)	326.17	Despite the increase in NCRE participation, rising demand and high participation of fossil sources result in high CO2 emissions. Possibility of shortage from 2035 and upward trend in marginal costs.
Scenario 3A - Trend increase	17,664.35 GWh (55.00%)	14,452.65 GWh (45.00%)	185.10	High focus on NCRE with a 55% participation. No shortage foreseen and marginal costs remain stable. Moderate and sustained increase in generation based on renewables.
Scenario 3B - Alternative increase	21,331.08 GWh (54.00%)	18,170.92 GWh (46.00%)	275.54	Significant increase in NCRE participation. Requires new thermal generation towards the end of the evaluated period. Demand growth is mainly covered by natural gas and NCRE.
Scenario 3C - Sensitivity CNE	15,094.99 GWh (47.00%)	17,022.01 GWh (53.00%)	213.20	Variant of Scenario 3B without the execution of the Las Placetas hydroelectric project and RSU projects. Slight increase in marginal costs, with no shortage expected.
Scenario 3D - Goal NCRE	20,554.88 GWh (64.00%)	11,562.12 GWh (36.00%)	153.63	Strong push for NCRE to meet environmental targets, with a 64% participation of NCRE.

3. Results

Upon analyzing the increase in demand within the energy matrix (Y) for the energy sector, while keeping the generation conditions of both fossil and non-fossil fuels constant from the baseline scenario up to the year 2035 for the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario, a significant variation was observed. This variation is reflected in the comparative decrease in emissions between this baseline scenario and other alternative scenarios over time.

In the graphical representation of the results, the increase in emissions under the baseline scenario is depicted in blue, whereas the reduction in emissions, expressed in millions of tons of CO2 equivalent greenhouse gases, is shown in the other scenarios. This reduction aligns with the expectations set forth by the indicative plan and the decarbonization objectives of the energy sector.

To assess the impact on sectors with strong correlations and those not directly related, a comparison was made with the baseline scenario, revealing the increase in emissions from the starting point (baseline) of each sector.

The primary finding was a significant increase in emissions in the sectors with the highest contributions, starting from 200,000 tons of CO2 for each sector evaluated. This result underscores the importance of implementing more effective mitigation measures and decarbonization strategies to counter the projected increase in emissions under the BAU scenario.

This highlights the imperative to enhance energy efficiency in response to rising demand and to conduct multisectoral analyses, such as the MARIO model, to account for collateral emissions in the expansion plans of each sector.

4. Discussion

This study emphasizes the critical role of renewable energy in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, particularly in the energy sector (Comision Nacional de Energia, 2022). Despite the benefits of renewables, the increasing energy demand poses a challenge by potentially raising emissions. Therefore, a broader approach focusing on enhancing energy efficiency across various sectors is essential, alongside expanding renewable energy capacities.

Improving energy efficiency is pivotal, not just for environmental benefits but also for economic resilience and energy security. Technologies such as smart grids and policies like tax incentives for energy-efficient practices can drive significant advancements in this area.

However, the study faces limitations, including its concentrated focus on the energy sector which might overlook emissions from other sectors. The reliance on current data and methodologies could also restrict the scope for considering future technological innovations and economic shifts.

Future research should adopt a more holistic perspective, incorporating emissions from all sectors using comprehensive methodologies like MARIO. This approach will allow for a deeper understanding of emissions contributions and the effectiveness of various interventions. Investigating emerging technologies, such as carbon capture and advanced renewables, and evaluating policy frameworks that support a low-carbon transition, will also be crucial.

In sum, while renewable energy is vital for mitigating climate change, an integrated strategy emphasizing energy efficiency and sector-wide emissions reduction is necessary. Addressing this study's limitations and exploring new areas can lead to more robust solutions for a sustainable energy future.

5. Conclusion

This study underlines the indispensable role of renewable energy in curbing greenhouse gas emissions, particularly within the energy sector. However, the findings also illuminate the complex challenge posed by rising energy demands, which can offset the environmental gains from renewables. The key lesson learned is the necessity of a dual approach that not only embraces renewable energy expansion but also prioritizes comprehensive energy efficiency across all sectors to truly mitigate emissions.

Recommendations from this study advocate for a broader adoption of energy-efficient technologies and practices, supported by policies that incentivize sustainable energy use. Future strategies should integrate a holistic view of emissions, considering the contributions from all sectors and employing advanced methodologies for a more

inclusive analysis. By addressing these recommendations, stakeholders can forge a path towards a more sustainable and resilient energy future, effectively balancing the demands of development with environmental stewardship.

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